

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SLEEP PATTERNS AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN MAKURDI, BENUE STATE

BY

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Abstract

This research explores the relationship between sleep patterns and academic performance among senior secondary school students in Makurdi, Benue State. Two research objectives, and two hypotheses guided the study. The study employs a correlational survey design. The population of the study consisted of six thousand seven hundred and sixty-three (6763) public senior secondary school students in Makurdi, Benue state. Simple random sampling was used to select 300 students from 15 senior secondary schools in Makurdi. The sample size was taking using the research advisor (2006) table of sample selection. Data was collected using two standardized instruments: Sleep Patterns and Academic Performance Questionnaire (SPAAPQ) and students' average scores from the most recent term results was used as academic performance. Descriptive and inferential statistics was used to analyze the data. Result review that positive moderate correlation exists ($r = 0.41$, $p < 0.05$) between sleep patterns and academic performance. Result shows a statistically significant difference in academic performance between students with regular sleep patterns and those with irregular sleep patterns ($t = 3.79$, $p = 0.000$). the findings emphasis the need for schools, parents, and policymakers to prioritize student sleep health as part of academic support strategies. Encouraging consistent bedtimes, reducing screen time before sleep, and educating students on the benefits of proper sleep may significantly improve academic performance and general well-being.

Keywords: Sleep Patterns, Academic Performance, Relationship

Introduction

Rest is crucial for the cognitive, emotional, and physical growth of teenagers. It is widely acknowledged as a fundamental biological process that is vital for learning, the consolidation of memory, and success in academics (Hirshkowitz, Whiton, Albert, Alessi, Bruni, DonCarlos, & Croft, 2015). Nonetheless, during the teenage years, sleep patterns frequently become inconsistent due to a mix of biological changes, academic demands, and lifestyle choices, leading to ongoing sleep deprivation and reduced sleep quality (Carskadon, 2011). These disrupted sleep patterns can significantly affect students' academic performance, concentration, and overall functioning in school. The Cognitive Load Theory (Sweller, 1988) describes the limited capacity of the brain's working memory when it comes to processing information. Instructional design is most effective when it minimizes extraneous load,

freeing up more cognitive resources for significant processing and permanent retention.

The idea of sleep patterns includes various components such as sleep length, quality, and regularity. Sleep length refers to the total hours of sleep received, quality pertains to how restful and uninterrupted that sleep is, and regularity involves keeping consistent bedtimes and wake-up times (Okano, Kaczmarzyk, Dave, Gabrieli, & Grossman, 2019). Research suggests that disturbances in any of these areas can negatively affect working memory, lessen attention span, and hinder information processing speed, all of which are crucial for academic achievement (Dewald, Meijer, Oort, Kerkhof, & Bögels, 2010).

This implies that adequate sleep replenishes attentional resources and optimizes working

memory capacity. Sleep deprivation increases intrinsic load (difficulty from the content itself feels heavier) and extraneous load (mental effort wasted on distractions), which hinders information processing in class. By analyzing the connection between sleep duration, quality, and consistency with academic performance, the research can determine if inadequate sleep habits lead to cognitive strain, resulting in diminished learning effectiveness and poorer academic results.

The Sleep–Wake Cycle Theory, based on studies of circadian rhythms, details how biological clocks control cycles of sleep and wakefulness throughout a 24-hour day (Moore-Ede, Sulzman, & Fuller, 1982). The release of hormones (such as melatonin) and external factors (like light and dark cycles) work together to determine the best times for sleep and mental engagement. According to this theory, students with disrupted sleep schedules (for example, going to bed late and getting up early for school) might suffer from "social jet lag," which can result in decreased alertness in the morning and diminished focus during lessons.

Secondary school students, particularly those at the senior level, are under increasing academic demands that often lead them to compromise their sleep in favour of study time or social activities (Beattie Kyle, Espie, & Biello, 2015). Research indicates that, insufficient or irregular sleep can result in decreased alertness, impaired memory, and diminished concentration, all of which adversely impact academic performance (Lo, Ong, Leong, Gooley, & Chee, 2016; Shochat, Cohen-Zion, & Tzischinsky, 2014). Conversely, students who adhere to consistent and adequate sleep patterns typically excel academically and exhibit better emotional resilience and cognitive flexibility.

In Nigeria, particularly in urban areas like Makurdi, students encounter various

distractions such as extra-classes after school hours, lots of assignment, TV, mobile devices, and social media, which frequently lead to later bedtimes and shorter sleep durations (Adeyemo, Ogunleye, & Alabi, 2020). Despite the escalating concern, there is a lack of local empirical studies directly investigating the correlation between sleep habits and academic performance among secondary school students. Understanding this relationship is essential for informing stakeholders, teachers, parents, and policy-makers on how to assist students in forming healthy sleep patterns that improve their academic outcome.

This research aims to investigate the connection between sleep habits and academic achievement among senior secondary school students in Makurdi, Benue State. By recognizing these patterns and their effects, the study aims to enhance strategies that promote students' academic performance through improved sleep hygiene.

Statement of the Problem

As academic demands on adolescents increase, concerns about their sleep patterns have become increasingly prevalent. Research indicates that, many adolescents do not achieve the recommended sleep duration, often resulting in sleep deprivation, irregular sleep schedules, and poor sleep quality. These sleep disturbances are exacerbated by factors such as academic pressures, technological distractions, and social commitments, leading to significant implications for adolescents' health and educational outcomes.

Despite the recognized importance of adequate sleep for cognitive functioning and emotional well-being, there remains a notable gap in empirical research examining the specific relationship between sleep patterns and academic performance in this demographic. Many studies have addressed

the consequences of sleep deprivation; for example, Okano, Kaczmarzyk, Dave, Gabrieli, & Grossman (2019) specifically noted that, although numerous studies connect sleep with cognitive abilities, there is a “deficiency of quantitative data utilizing objective measures” in evaluating the relationship between sleep and academic achievement. Additionally, there is a lack of research concentrating on senior secondary students in particular urban Nigerian areas (such as Makurdi, Benue State), where cultural, socio-economic, and school-schedule elements may distinctly influence sleep habits and their effects on academic performance. Furthermore, the specific impacts of sleep duration, quality, and timing/consistency on academic achievement within this group have not been thoroughly explored. By addressing these areas, we can better understand whether interventions (such as sleep hygiene education, schedule modifications, and parental support) might effectively enhance academic outcomes in Nigerian secondary schools.

Lund, Reider, Whiting, and Prichard (2024) examined first-year medical students and discovered that inadequate sleep quality and daytime sleepiness had a significant adverse effect on both academic performance and GPA. However, few have comprehensively analyzed how various aspects of sleep such as duration, quality, and consistency interact with academic achievement.

In particular, the lack of clarity regarding how these sleep factors contribute to or hinder academic performance poses challenges for educators, parents, and policymakers aiming to support adolescents in their educational pursuits. Furthermore, understanding the nuances of this relationship is critical for developing effective interventions that promote healthier sleep habits among adolescents. Therefore, this study seeks to investigate the relationship between sleep

patterns and academic performance in adolescents, aiming to provide valuable insights that can inform strategies for enhancing student academic performance and overall well-being.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are to:

1. determine whether a relationship exists between sleep patterns and academic performance of senior secondary school students in Makurdi.
2. Access the difference in academic performance of students with regular sleep pattern and those with irregular sleep patterns

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested:

1. There is no significant relationship between sleep patterns and academic performance of senior secondary school students in Makurdi.
2. There is no significant difference in academic performance between students with regular sleep patterns and those with irregular sleep patterns.

Methodology

This research adopts a correlational survey approach. The design is suitable since the objective of the study is to explore the relationship between two factors; sleep habits and academic performance without manipulating either of the variables. The population of this study comprises of 6783 senior secondary school students in public schools within Makurdi Local Government Area, Benue State. This population is chosen because students at this level often experience high academic pressure, making them a relevant group for studying the influence on sleep pattern on academic performance. A total of 250 students were chosen using the simple random sampling technique so as to

give everyone a chance to participate in the research.

A structured questionnaire was designed by researchers, named the “Sleep Patterns and Academic Performance Questionnaire (SPAAPQ),” for the purpose of data collection. The instrument comprises two sections, Section A comprises of Information on demographics while section B Items evaluate sleep patterns (such as typical sleep duration, consistency of bedtime, quality of sleep, and time of waking). The items were assessed using a 4-point Likert scale (Never, Sometimes, Often, Always). Academic performance was collected from the students’ average scores from their most recent term results, collected with the consent of the school authorities.

The face and content validity of the instrument was ensured through expert review by two educational psychologists and one measurement and evaluation expert. To determine reliability, a trial test was conducted in government secondary school, Vadekya. This school was not part of the sampled population but has the same characteristics as the study population. The reliability coefficient was calculated using Cronbach’s Alpha, result review the reliability index of .70.

Data were collected by the researcher with the assistance of the school teachers assigned to

her at each school. Permission were sought from school principals before administering the questionnaires. The questionnaire was administered during break periods to avoid disrupting classes. Participation was voluntary, and confidentiality was assured.

The data collected were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25. Descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation was used to summarize students’ sleep patterns and academic performance. Inferential statistics used include; Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation to test the relationship between sleep patterns and academic performance, and Independent samples t-test to determine differences in academic performance between students with regular and irregular sleep patterns. All hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Hypotheses one

What is the relationship between sleep patterns and academic performance of senior secondary school students in Makurdi?

Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to determine the significant relationship between sleep patterns (measured through duration, quality, and consistency) and academic performance (measured using term scores). The result is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Pearson Correlation between Sleep Patterns and Academic Performance

Variables	N	r	p	Decision
Sleep Patterns & Academic performance	250	0.41	0.000	significant

P = 0.000 < 0.05, correlation is significant at the 0.05

The result in Table 1 shows a positive moderate correlation (r = 0.41, p < 0.05) between sleep patterns and academic performance. This implies that students with

better (more regular and sufficient) sleep patterns tend to perform better academically. Thus, sleep patterns are significantly related to academic achievement.

Based on the result in Table 1 ($r = 0.41, p = 0.000$), the null hypothesis is rejected. This indicates that a statistically significant relationship exists between students' sleep patterns and their academic performance.

Hypothesis Two; **There is no significant difference in academic performance between students with regular sleep**

patterns and those with irregular sleep patterns.

To test this hypothesis, students were grouped into two categories based on their sleep habits: regular sleepers ($n = 140$) and irregular sleepers ($n = 110$). An independent samples t-test was conducted to compare their mean academic performance scores. The result is shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Independent Samples t-test result

Group	N	M	SD	t	p	Decision
Regula Sleepers	140	74.4	8.56	3.79	0.000	Significant
Irregular sleepers	110	67.2	9.34			

The result in Table 2 shows a statistically significant difference in academic performance between students with regular sleep patterns and those with irregular sleep patterns ($t = 3.79, p = 0.000$). Students with regular sleep patterns performed better on average. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant difference in academic performance between students with regular sleep patterns and those with irregular sleep patterns is here by rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The results of this study revealed a significant positive relationship between sleep patterns and academic performance among senior secondary school students in Makurdi. Specifically, students who reported regular and sufficient sleep exhibited higher academic performance, while those with irregular sleep patterns performed relatively poorly. This finding aligns with prior research which has consistently shown that sleep is a crucial factor for cognitive functioning, memory consolidation, and academic success (Lo, Ong, Leong, Gooley, & Chee, 2016; Shochat, Cohen-Zion, & Tzischinsky, 2014).

The correlation coefficient ($r = 0.41, p < 0.05$) suggests a moderate positive relationship,

implying that as the quality and regularity of sleep improve, academic performance tends to increase. This supports the findings of Carskadon (2011), who emphasized that, adolescent sleep deprivation negatively impacts attention, executive function, and problem-solving abilities skills essential for learning and academic achievement.

Furthermore, the t-test results indicated a statistically significant difference in academic performance between students with regular sleep patterns and those with irregular sleep patterns. Students who maintained a consistent sleep schedule scored higher on academic assessments compared to their peers with inconsistent or inadequate sleep routines. This result reinforces the conclusion by Beattie, Kyle, Espie, and Biello (2015) that, healthy sleep hygiene is associated with better school outcomes and emotional stability in adolescents.

These results align with the Cognitive Load Theory (CLT) perspective (Sweller, 1988), as adequate and consistent sleep enhances working memory capacity, attentional control, and the speed of information processing. When students are adequately rested, Intrinsic cognitive load becomes more manageable,

challenging subjects seem less mentally taxing, extraneous cognitive load is minimized and students can concentrate without experiencing mental fatigue, germane load (efforts directed toward learning) is optimized more energy is allocated to understanding and retaining information.

Conversely, poor sleep habits can overwhelm cognitive resources, making it more difficult to encode, consolidate, and recall information during classes and examinations. The identified moderate correlation ($r = 0.41$) suggests that sleep is not the only factor influencing academic achievement, yet it significantly aids in preventing cognitive overload and improving learning efficiency.

The Sleep–Wake Cycle Theory (Moore-Ede et al., 1982) suggests that, circadian rhythms in the body determine the best times for alertness, learning, and memory. A consistent and sufficient sleep–wake cycle synchronizes students’ peak cognitive abilities with their school timetables. The findings of this study indicate that students who adhere to regular bedtimes and wake-up times—thereby reducing “social jet lag” - (misalignment between a person’s natural biological clock and their socially imposed schedule) exhibit greater alertness during school hours, experience improved sustained attention, and can participate more actively in learning. Disrupted sleep cycles, which are prevalent among teenagers who go to bed late and rise early for school, can lead to chronic sleep deficiency and diminished morning alertness, ultimately resulting in poorer academic performance.

In the context of Nigeria, Adeyemo Ogunleye, and Alabi (2020) also observed that many secondary school students face sleep challenges due to late-night use of electronic devices and academic overload, leading to

poor academic performance. The findings of the current study reflect similar trends in Makurdi, suggesting that the issue of irregular sleep and its impact on school success is a widespread concern that requires urgent attention. Reducing screen time before sleep, and educating students on the benefits of proper sleep may significantly improve academic performance and general well-being.

Implications of the Study

The findings of this study have several important implications for educators, parents, policymakers, and students:

For School Administrators and Teachers:

The positive relationship between sleep patterns and academic performance highlights the need for schools to consider the impact of school schedules and workloads on students' sleep habits. Educators should discourage excessive homework or late-night study routines that interfere with students' rest.

For Parents and Guardians:

Parents play a critical role in regulating their children’s sleep habits. By setting consistent bedtimes, monitoring screen time before bed, and creating a conducive sleep environment, they can support students' academic performance and overall health.

For Students:

Students need to be educated about the value of sleep and how their sleep behaviors can affect their cognitive abilities and academic outcomes. Promoting sleep hygiene awareness could help students make better lifestyle choices.

For Policymakers and Curriculum Planners:

The findings suggest that, policies aimed at improving students’ well-being should include sleep education as part of health or life skills curricula. Schools should also consider

starting academic activities later in the morning to accommodate the biological sleep needs of adolescents.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Schools should organize health and wellness workshops to educate students about the importance of healthy sleep patterns and their impact on academic success.
2. Parents should monitor and guide their children's daily routines, including screen time and bedtime activities, to ensure adequate sleep.
3. Educational authorities should consider reviewing school start times in line with global best practices that support adolescent sleep health.
4. Further research should be conducted across other regions of Nigeria with a larger and more diverse sample size to validate the generalizability of these findings.

Conclusion

This study investigated the relationship between sleep patterns and academic performance among senior secondary school students in Makurdi, Benue State. The results showed a significant positive relationship between the two variables, indicating that students who maintain regular and sufficient sleep routines performed better academically. Additionally, a significant difference in academic performance was found between students with regular and irregular sleep patterns, in favour of the former. These findings underscore the importance of healthy sleep habits for academic success and highlight the need for collaborative efforts by schools, families, and policymakers to support students' well-being through structured sleep hygiene education and lifestyle support.

References

- Adeyemo, D. A., Ogunleye, A. J., & Alabi, O. T. (2020). Sleep quality and academic performance among adolescents in a Nigerian secondary school. *Nigerian Journal of Clinical Psychology*, 18(2), 112–123.
- Beattie, L., Kyle, S. D., Espie, C. A., & Biello, S. M. (2015). Social interactions, emotion regulation, and mood during daily life: Examining the role of sleep. *Sleep Health*, 1(2), 121–127. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sleh.2015.02.008>
- Carskadon, M. A. (2011). Sleep in adolescents: The perfect storm. *Pediatric Clinics of North America*, 58(3), 637–647. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pcl.2011.03.003>
- Dewald, J. F., Meijer, A. M., Oort, F. J., Kerkhof, G. A., & Bögels, S. M. (2010). The influence of sleep quality, sleep duration and sleepiness on school performance in children and adolescents: A meta-analytic review. *Sleep Medicine*, 14(3), 179–189. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sleep.2009.10.017>
- Hirshkowitz, M., Whiton, K., Albert, S. M., Alessi, C., Bruni, O., DonCarlos, L., ... & Croft, J. B. (2015). National Sleep Foundation's sleep time duration recommendations: Methodology and results summary. *Sleep Health*, 1(1), 40–43. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sleh.2014.12.010>
- Lund, H. G., Reider, B. D., Whiting, A. B., & Prichard, J. R. (2024). Sleep patterns and predictors of disturbed sleep in a large population of college students. *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 74(3), 389–396. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jadohealth.2023.10.012>
- Lo, J. C., Ong, J. L., Leong, R. L., Gooley, J. J., & Chee, M. W. (2016). Cognitive performance, sleepiness, and mood in partially sleep deprived adolescents: The need for sleep study. *Sleep*, 39(3), 687–698. <https://doi.org/10.5665/sleep.5552>

- Moore-Ede, M. C., Sulzman, F. M., & Fuller, C. A. (1982). *The clocks that time us: Physiology of the circadian timing system*. Harvard University Press.
- Okano, K., Kaczmarzyk, J. R., Dave, N., Gabrieli, J. D. E., & Grossman, J. C. (2019). Sleep quality, duration, and consistency are associated with better academic performance in college students. *npj Science of Learning*, 4, Article 16. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41539-019-0055-z>
- Shochat, T., Cohen-Zion, M., & Tzischinsky, O. (2014). Functional consequences of inadequate sleep in adolescents: A systematic review. *Sleep Medicine Reviews*, 18(1), 75–87. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.smrv.2013.03.005>
- Sweller, J. (1988). Cognitive load during problem solving: Effects on learning. *Cognitive Science*, 12(2), 257–285. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15516709cog1202_4